

TRANSFORMING HIGHER EDUCATION IN THE DIGITAL ERA: THE ROLE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN DRIVING INNOVATION AND SOCIAL CO-CREATION

NOER RAFIKAH ZULYANTI ¹, AMIARTUTI KUSMANINGTYAS ^{2*} and
ABDUL HALIK ³

^{1,2,3} Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya, Indonesia.

*Corresponding Author Email: amiartuti@untag-sby.ac.id

Abstract

The research investigates the impact of social media on customer citizenship behaviour and customer participation behaviour, as well as its effect on service innovation and social co-creation as moderating factors. This study adopts a quantitative approach and involves 170 student respondents affiliated with LPTNU in Province East Java, Indonesia. The data collected was analysed using SEM-PLS version 3.0. The results of the overall research justify the dominant logic theory of service and the interesting findings in this study are that in higher education environments, student engagement to generate new excellence or create creative things for more innovative services, only triggered by social media marketing activities. Social Co-creation is not able to moderate the influence of customer citizenship behaviour and customer participation behaviour on service innovation. The novelty of the research lies in the conceptual framework model by adding the role of social media. Therefore, colleges should always facilitate collaborative social interaction and provide student dialogue space to improve service facilities that can be provided through social media platforms.

Keywords: Customer Citizenship, Customer Participation, Dominant Logic Theory, Marketing, Service Innovation, Social Co-Creation and Social Media.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's competitive business landscape, the rapid market dynamics demand sustainable innovation. The business climate has seen radical changes in the previous few years (Aouad & Aboueljaouad, 2019). The Company faces greater competitors and potentially more efficient, emphasizing the importance of innovation's role in acquiring and maintaining competitive advantage (Flores et al., 2015). This competition also applies to service-oriented companies. The service sector continues to grow, dominating the development of the global economy. Innovative services are essential metrics for organizational innovation capabilities that are empirically associated with market competitive advantage and superior performance (Y.-Q. Li & Liu, 2019).

Innovation is essential for business continuity in the fast-paced world of today (Moghadamzadeh et al., 2020). The innovative service reflects the introduction of something new to customers, which aims to improve services and generate perceived value (Hollebeek et al., 2018). Innovation in the service sector is converting concepts into fresh offerings that set a business apart from rivals (Demary, 2017). Even in the field of higher education, there is a boost to innovation and creativity in the service sector. Libraries in colleges for example, play an

important role in growing science in the community. Within this framework, the study intends to explore the significance of creative services, with an emphasis on social media marketing initiatives, consumer participation, citizenship, and social shared production within the academic setting. Social media marketing's effects on customer citizenship and participation behaviour, and how that influences service innovation, remains largely unexamined despite an increase in studies. Previous research suggested the need to investigate social media activities as a driver of behaviour and participation of citizens (Foroudi et al., 2019). Furthermore, studies Barile et al. (2020) highlight the need of strategically managing social media platforms to encourage collaboration and innovation. This realization makes it possible to investigate how social media marketing efforts affect shared creation behaviours, which will ultimately enhance service innovation. Research ideas that include social media marketing activities broaden and replicate models Moghadamzadeh et al. (2020) in light of these potential. By bringing attention to the as-yet-unstudied connection between social media usage, consumer behaviour, and service innovation in academic settings, the new framework seeks to advance current understanding. The research will fill the gap by testing it on students in the LPTNU (Higher Education Institute of Nahdlatul Ulama) in East Java Province-Indonesia, providing insight into student behaviour as the main user of social media who contributes significantly to fostering innovation and adding value in university settings.

The study's objective is to clarify the nuanced ways that social media affects consumer behaviour and service innovation and offer a fresh interpretation of the Dominant Service Logic theory and provide practical insight to universities who want to improve their service innovation through social media engagement.

2. METHODS

This study falls under the category of explanatory or confirmatory research. The explanation's scope indicates that this study encompasses causality research, which is defined as research that looks for explanations in the shape of causal relationships between certain ideas, variables, or management techniques. This research aims to describe the causal relationship between independent variables, namely social media marketing activities, mediation variables, specifically, consumer participation and citizenship behaviour dependent variables namely service innovation, and moderation variables are social joint creations tested at LPTNU students in East Java Province, Indonesia.

In this research, the population is students who are under the auspices of LPTNU in East Java Province, Indonesia. Based on the research population criteria, there is one college that provides services to its students, both academic and non-academic administrative services on one platform.

The population criteria in this study are as follows:

- Universities that provide services to students that are integrated in one platform (both academic and non-academic administration services).
- Students are active users of Instagram social media.

The number of students with the criteria as mentioned is not yet known with certainty, so the population of this study is also not known with certainty.

The Lemeshow formula was used to calculate the sample size in this investigation because the precise population size is unknown. To find the number of study samples with a 10% sampling error, apply the following formula:

$$n = (Z^2 P(1-P))/d^2$$

Information:

n: Number of Samples

Z: normal table value at $1-\alpha/2$ confidence level

P: proportion

d: precision

The number of samples in this study can be determined using the formula above in the following way:

$$n = (1.96^2 \times 0.5 (1-0.5))/0.1^2$$

$$n = 96.04$$

Using the formula Lemeshow above as a guide, the lowest sample size is 96. In this study, 170 respondents met the population criteria for samples.

The population criteria outlined above dictate the use of purposive sampling as the sampling method. In this research, the instrument of questionnaire research is a set of statements aimed at respondents to obtain answers and approvals. Questionnaires are shared with respondents via Google Form link.

A collection of respondent statements is compiled using the variable indicators, which are derived from the variables to be measured. Selecting an answer from the list is how statements are measured. On the Likert scale, each response is given a score between 1 and 5. An individual's or a group's attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions of social phenomena can be evaluated using the Likert Scale. According to Ferdinand (2014), there are five degrees or rankings (ordinal scale) on the Likert scale in use. Classification Five points for Strongly Agree, four for Category Agree, three for Neutral Category, two for Category Disagree, and one for Category Strongly Disagree. The data collected will be analysed using SEM-PLS version 3.0.

3. RESULTS

Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model)

In the examination of the measurement model, the researcher performed various assessments, specifically the validity test and the reliability test.

Figure 1: Results of Research Model

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

Outer Model Evaluation

The assessment of the measurement model, commonly referred to as the outer model, is done to find out how latent variables and their indicators relate to one another. The measurement model's validity and reliability are evaluated. The objective is to verify the model's validity and assess the constructs' dependability in light of empirical theory and research (Henseler et al., 2016). Construct validity testing is done using discriminant validity and convergent validity. To make sure that each latent variable's concept is unique from the conceptions of other latent variables, the assessment of discriminant validity is conducted and to assess the link between a construct's manifest variable and the manifest variable of another construct in a structural model. Discriminant validity can be assessed based on the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio. Heterotrait is used to test whether there is a correlation between indicators or whether indicators have low contributions in measuring certain constructs. HTMT testing can help identify inconsistent or irrelevant indicators. Additionally, a convergent validity test is employed in a construct reliability test to examine the link between variables that manifest in a concept. The goal of convergent validity is to determine the reliability of each connection made between an indicator and its latent variable or construct. If the external loadings exceed 0.70 and convergent validity testing can be assessed based on these two criteria, the average variance extracted (AVE) exceeds 0.50. Test convergent validity is evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha, Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and Composite Reliability (CR). Cronbach's Alpha gauges a construct's degree of reliability. The reliability of every indication in the model is reflected in

this value. The true dependability value of a construct is measured by composite reliability. CR evaluates each indicator's dependability value in relation to a given variable. It is thought that composite dependability is more accurate in determining a construct's internal consistency. On the other hand, each construct's and latent variable's discriminant validity is assessed using AVE. If a construct has a Cronbach Alpha coefficient higher than 0.7, it is considered dependable. CR exceeds 0.7 and AVE is at least 0.5 (Henseler et al., 2016).

Construct Validity Test Results

Discriminant validity can be assessed based on the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio. Heterotrait is used to test whether there is a correlation between indicators or whether indicators have low contributions in measuring certain constructs. HTMT testing can help identify inconsistent or irrelevant indicators. Based on statistical tests, the entire construct HTMT value should be lower than 0.85 although there are some theories that recommend the HTMT limit lower than 0.90 (Henseler et al., 2016). In this study, the HTMT limit is smaller than 0.90. Statistics derived from the research findings indicate that the value of HTMT obtained from all constructs is less than 0.90 (Table 1). Thus, the entire construct has a valid measurement instrument.

Table 1: Result of Discriminant Validity Test with HTMT

Variable	Z1	Z2	Z3	Y	X
Z1					
Z2	0.68				
Z3	0.646	0.83			
Y	0.728	0.878	0.705		
X	0.702	0.729	0.614	0.731	

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

Construct Reliability Test Results

The study's reliability assessment involved Cronbach Alpha, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Should the Cronbach Alpha score exceed 0.7, based on the reliability test findings, the reliability is considered acceptable, the entire construct is deemed reliable. AVE must be at least 0.5 and Composite Reliability must be more than 0.7 (Henseler et al., 2016). Using Cronbach Alpha criteria, Table 2 reliability test findings show that all constructs have values over 0.7, with Customer Citizenship Behaviour having the greatest value, which is 0.942. Thus, from reliability test using Cronbach Alpha, the entire construct has good internal consistency to use in testing this model. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values are used in reliability testing; however, the results display the lowest AVE value of the entire construct that is greater than 0.5 (Table 2). The value is equal to the minimum required in reliability analysis using AVE parameters. This demonstrates that the study's variables and indicators have good internal consistency to be used in analysing relationships between variables. Therefore, it is evident that all the variables in this research are deemed reliable, as demonstrated by an AVE value of at least 0.5, a Composite Reliability of at least 0.7, and a Cronbach Alpha exceeding 0.7.

Table 2: Construct Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
X	0.928	0.931	0.939	0.607
Y	0.894	0.896	0.922	0.702
Z1	0.942	0.942	0.952	0.714
Z2	0.887	0.892	0.912	0.598
Z3	0.89	0.897	0.923	0.751

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

Inner Model Evaluation

Structural model evaluation (inner model) is used to predict or show a specific cause relationship between latent or variable variables that cannot be measured directly. Evaluation of inner models with PLS in this study used the Coefficient determination parameters (R^2) to examine the connection and importance among variables within the model (Hair Jr et al., 2014; Henseler et al., 2016).

Table 3: Coefficient of determination (R^2) Test Results

Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Z1	0.446	0.443
Z2	0.445	0.441
Y	0.709	0.698

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

According to the analysis of the coefficient of determination as shown in Table 3, the value of the R^2 contribution of social media marketing activity to the variability of client citizens' behavior is 0.446 (moderate). Then the R^2 value contributes social media marketing activity to the variability of customer participation behavior of 0.445 (moderate) while the R^2 value contributes social media marketing activity to the variability of service innovation of 0.709 (strong).

Hypothesis Test Results

The explanation provided pertains to the results obtained from the hypothesis testing about each study variable's direct influence.

Table 4: Path Coefficients Test Results

Relationship	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	T Statistic	P Value
X → Z1	0.668	0.671	11.073	0
X → Z2	0.667	0.674	7.471	0
Z1 → Y	0.256	0.263	2.679	0.008
Z2 → Y	0.522	0.501	4.512	0
Moderating Z1*Z3 → Y	-0.13	-0.112	1.934	0.054
Moderating Z2*Z3 → Y	0.071	0.079	0.899	0.369

Source: Researcher's results (2024)

H1: Social Media Marketing Activities have significant relationship with Customer Citizenship Behavior.

The test's findings demonstrated that social media marketing activity had an impact on service innovativeness; the p-value was 0.000, or $P < 0.05$, and the t-statistic value of 11,073 was significant.

The test's findings indicate that social media marketing activity significantly and favorably influences service innovation. Service Innovation increases with the amount of customization and entertaining drive social media marketing efforts, engagement, E-WOM, and trendiness. So, hypothesis (H1) is acceptable.

H2: Social Media Marketing Activities have significant relationship with Customer Participation Behavior.

Based on how consumer participation behavior relates to the study, the findings revealed a 0.000 p-value, or $P < 0.05$, and t-statistics (7,471), indicating significant test results. As a result, customer participation behavior is positively and significantly impacted by social media marketing activities.

Consumer involvement in seeking information, exchanging information, and exhibiting responsible conduct, and in-person interactions increases with the amount of social media marketing activities driven by entertainment, adjustment, engagement, E-WOM, and trends. So, hypothesis (H2) is acceptable.

H3: Customer Citizenship Behavior has a significant relationship with Service Innovativeness.

The examination findings revealed that customer citizenship behavior plays a crucial and beneficial role in driving service innovation, as demonstrated by the t-statistic value of 2.679 and the less than 0.05 p-value of 0.008.

The higher the Customer Citizenship Behavior triggered by feedback behavior factors, advocacy, help and tolerance, the Innovative Service will be increasing with new service concepts, good client interfaces, satisfactory service systems and the right technology options. So, hypothesis (H3) is acceptable.

H4: Customer Participation Behavior has a significant relationship with Service Innovativeness.

Upon reviewing the correlation between Service Innovativeness and Customer Participation Behavior, a 0.000 p-value and a t-statistic value of 4,512 were found, denoting statistical significance, were obtained ($P < 0.05$). As a result, Service Innovativeness is positively and significantly impacted by Customer Participation Behavior.

The more customers participate in the process, the more service innovation is enhanced through information exchange, responsible conduct, information searching, and interpersonal interactions. So, hypothesis (H4) is acceptable.

H5: Social Co-Creation plays a moderating role in the relationship between Customer Citizenship Behavior and Service Innovativeness.

Moderation variable testing Social Co-Creation in customer citizenship behavior relationship resulted in t-statistic value (1,934) which means smaller than t-table (1,975) so that statistically test results are outside the critical area. And the value of P-value 0.054 or P-value >0.05 means the test results are insignificant. Therefore, the hypothesis (H5) that contends that Customer Citizenship Behavior has a moderating effect on Social Co-Creation's influence on Service Innovativeness is rejected.

H6: Social Co-Creation plays a moderating role in the connection between Customer Participation Behavior and Service Innovativeness.

The Social Co-Creation test's t-statistic score of 0.899 indicates a less significant effect of customer engagement behavior on service innovativeness than the t-table (1.975). In addition, if the P-value is 0.054 or higher than 0.05, the test results are not significant. As a result, the hypothesis (H6) that suggests that Customer Participation Behavior Influences Service Innovativeness while Social Co-Creation moderates that effect is rejected.

4. DISCUSSION

The influence between exogenous variables is further analyzed to get more comprehensive discussion. This is in harmony with the aim that The results of this study can be taken into account to enhance creative services for students of LPTNU Province East Java, Indonesia. Discussion of the influence between variables in this study can be explained below.

The study's findings show a strong positive correlation between social media marketing campaigns and good customer citizenship practices. The study emphasizes how social media marketing affects students' conduct in a classroom, as seen by t-statistical values that beyond the t-table.

The study identifies five indicators of social media marketing activities, highlighting their excellent correlation with customer citizenship behavior. Notably, interaction emerges as a key factor, strengthening overall social media marketing effectiveness. The positive impact on corporate citizenship behavior suggests students actively engage with university-owned social media, contributing constructive behavior and innovative ideas.

Aligned with M. L. Cheung et al. (2021), the study emphasizes that social media marketing encourages consumers, in this case, students, the importance of social media in influencing student citizenship behaviors is highlighted as they work to establish distinctive advantages for both brands and themselves, promoting advocacy, peer assistance, and tolerance.

The research recognizes the value of entertainment, interactivity, and trends in social media advertising, echoing the transformation of students from passive receivers to active value creators, as highlighted by (Hussain et al., 2022).

Validating the Dominant Logic Services theory, the study emphasizes how social media marketing campaigns have a significant impact on consumers' civic involvement. The

integration of customer resources, particularly through active problem-solving contributions via social media, strengthens this influence.

The study further explores the correlation between social media marketing activities and customer participation behavior. It establishes a positive and substantial association, confirming that greater social media marketing activities lead to higher customer participation behavior.

Specifically, the study focuses on the university's Instagram platform, highlighting its effectiveness in encouraging student participation behavior. It aligns with (Ren et al., 2021), emphasizing that consumer participation behavior is triggered by emotions. The entertaining social media activities inspire active participation, with students sharing resources and engaging virtually.

The study M. L. Cheung et al. (2021) highlights the university's social media as a two-way communication facilitator, enabling idea exchange between students and information sharing. It corresponds to (Zadeh et al., 2019), showcasing students creating value through social networking services like Instagram.

Connecting to Seifert & Kwon (2020), the study emphasizes the impact of brand story-based e-WOM on personal interaction, a key indicator of customer participation behavior. It aligns with Kwon & Namkung (2022), emphasizing the significant impact of perceived value, especially in entertainment, on customer participation behavior.

The research demonstrates a strong and meaningful correlation between customer citizenship behavior and service innovativeness, confirming that higher customer citizenship behavior contributes to improved innovative services. This aligns with Gong & Yi (2021), linking customer voluntary behavior, such as feedback and advocacy, to university performance and innovation.

Results also correspond with Torkzadeh et al. (2021), emphasizing joint value creation by students in private universities. Feedback emerges as a crucial component, encouraging service providers to enhance quality through innovation.

The study validates the Dominant Logic Services theory, emphasizing the crucial role of students in creating shared values. Students play an active role by engaging in information retrieval, sharing, demonstrating responsible conduct, and participating in personal interactions, significantly influencing social media marketing activities on customer participation behavior.

Customer participation behavior is further explored in its positive and significant influence on service innovation. Students' active engagement, including sharing knowledge, being responsible, and interacting with others, correlates with improved service innovation.

These findings align with Q. Li & Pu (2020), verifying the beneficial influence of client involvement on creative service delivery. The study emphasizes the role of each indicator, particularly information search, in driving service innovation.

However, the study acknowledges a moderate influence between customer participation behavior and service innovation, possibly due to students prioritizing educational goals. This

aligns with Fotiadis (2019), which emphasizes the role of each indicator in driving service innovation.

The study's exploration of social co-creation reveals no appreciable moderating influence on the correlation between service innovation and consumer citizenship behavior. It challenges previous research, suggesting that the content of social shared creation may not be a motivating factor for students' citizenship behavior.

Similar inconsistencies are noted in research by Moghadamzadeh et al. (2020), where the impact of good customer citizenship on service innovation was lessened by social co-creation. The study emphasizes the scarcity of examinations in this aspect, pointing to implicit mentions in other studies.

Moreover, the study looks into how social co-creation moderates the association between customer engagement behavior and service innovation. However, results indicate no significant moderation effect, challenging the notion that Social Co-Creation plays a moderate role in influencing customer participation behavior and service innovation.

Contrary to previous research, the study emphasizes the importance of social media marketing activities over social shared creation content in encouraging student participation behavior and contributing to service innovation. This finding challenges the Service-Dominant Logic theory, which suggests that the co-creation process is triggered by the participation of both parties.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study highlights the crucial role of social media marketing activities in shaping student behaviours, influencing both customer citizenship behaviour and participation behaviour. It validates the Dominant Logic Services theory, emphasizing the active role of students in creating shared values and contributing to service innovation. The study challenges previous notions regarding the moderating influence of Social Co-Creation, emphasizing the importance of social media marketing in encouraging voluntary behaviour and collaboration between students and universities.

References

- 1) Aouad, Y., & Aboueljaouad, S. (2019). The Impact of Co-Creation with Customers on Service Innovation in the Moroccan Context. *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*, 9(2), 39–49. <https://doi.org/10.31033/ijemr.9.2.6>.
- 2) Barile, S., Grimaldi, M., Loia, F., & Sirianni, C. A. (2020). Technology, value co-creation and innovation in service ecosystems: Toward sustainable co-innovation. *Sustainability*, 12(7), 2759. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12072759>.
- 3) Chen, X., Jiao, C., Ji, R., & Li, Y. (2021). Examining customer motivation and its impact on customer engagement behavior in social media: the mediating effect of brand experience. *SAGE Open*, 11(4), 21582440211052256. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211052256>.
- 4) Cheng, C. C. J., Shiu, E. C. C., & Dawson, J. A. (2014). Service business model and service innovativeness. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 18(02), 1450013. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S1363919614500133>.

- 5) Cheung, M. F. Y., & To, W.-M. (2016). Service co-creation in social media: An extension of the theory of planned behavior. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 65, 260–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.08.031>.
- 6) Cheung, M. L., Pires, G. D., Rosenberger III, P. J., Leung, W. K. S., & Ting, H. (2021). Investigating the role of social media marketing on value co-creation and engagement: An empirical study in China and Hong Kong. *Australasian Marketing Journal*, 29(2), 118–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ausmj.2020.03.006>.
- 7) Chwialkowska, A. (2019). The effectiveness of brand-and customer-centric content strategies at generating shares, ‘likes’, and comments. *Journal of Promotion Management*, 25(2), 270–300. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10496491.2018.1443307>.
- 8) Demary, V. (2017). Stepping up the Game: The Role of Innovation in the Sharing Economy. IW-Report. <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/161427/1/887791751.pdf>.
- 9) Ding, X., You, X., Zhang, X., & Yu, Y. (2022). Can patients co-create value in an online healthcare platform? An examination of value co-creation. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(19), 12823. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191912823>.
- 10) Ferdinand, A. (2014). Metode penelitian manajemen: Pedoman penelitian untuk penulisan skripsi tesis dan disertasi ilmu manajemen.
- 11) Flores, R. L., Negny, S., Belaud, J. P., & Le Lann, J.-M. (2015). Collective intelligence to solve creative problems in conceptual design phase. *Procedia Engineering*, 131, 850–860. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2015.12.394>.
- 12) Foroudi, P., Yu, Q., Gupta, S., & Foroudi, M. M. (2019). Enhancing university brand image and reputation through customer value co-creation behaviour. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 138, 218–227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.09.006>.
- 13) Fotiadis, T. (2019). Customer participation, e-service quality, satisfaction:(e) Service dominant logic trinity. *Journal of Promotion Management*, 25(3), 394–418. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10496491.2019.1557818>.
- 14) Godey, B., Manthiou, A., Pederzoli, D., Rokka, J., Aiello, G., Donvito, R., & Singh, R. (2016). Social media marketing efforts of luxury brands: Influence on brand equity and consumer behavior. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(12), 5833–5841. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2016.04.181>.
- 15) Gong, T., & Yi, Y. (2021). A review of customer citizenship behaviors in the service context. *The Service Industries Journal*, 41(3–4), 169–199. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02642069.2019.1680641>.
- 16) Gummesson, E. (2011). Total relationship marketing. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780080880112>.
- 17) Hair Jr, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., & Kuppelwieser, V. G. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): An emerging tool in business research. *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106–121.
- 18) Henseler, J., Hubona, G., & Ray, P. A. (2016). Using PLS path modeling in new technology research: updated guidelines. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 116(1), 2–20. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-09-2015-0382>.
- 19) Hertog, P. Den. (2000). Knowledge-intensive business services as co-producers of innovation. *International Journal of Innovation Management*, 4(04), 491–528. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S136391960000024X>.
- 20) Hollebeek, L. D., W. Andreassen, T., Smith, D. L. G., Grönquist, D., Karahasanovic, A., & Marquez, A. (2018). Epilogue—service innovation actor engagement: an integrative model. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 32(1), 95–100. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSM-11-2017-0390>.
- 21) Hussain, A., Ting, D. H., & Mazhar, M. (2022). Driving consumer value co-creation and purchase intention by social media advertising value. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 800206. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.800206>.

- 22) Ketonen-Oksi, S., Jussila, J. J., & Kärkkäinen, H. (2016). Social media-based value creation and business models. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 116(8), 1820–1838. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IMDS-05-2015-0199>.
- 23) Kim, A. J., & Ko, E. (2012). Do social media marketing activities enhance customer equity? An empirical study of luxury fashion brand. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(10), 1480–1486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.10.014>.
- 24) Kim, E., Tang, L., & Bosselman, R. (2019). Customer perceptions of innovativeness: An accelerator for value co-creation. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 43(6), 807–838. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1096348019836273>.
- 25) Kwon, A.-M., & Namkung, Y. (2022). The Impact of the Perceived Values of Social Network Services (SNSs) on Brand Attitude and Value-Co-Creation Behavior in the Coffee Industry. *Sustainability*, 14(9), 5425. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095425>.
- 26) Li, Q., & Pu, J. (2020). How online reviews drive enterprise innovation: the intermediary role of customer participation. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1629(1), 12051. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1629/1/012051>.
- 27) Li, Y.-Q., & Liu, C.-H. (2019). The power of coworkers in service innovation: The moderating role of social interaction. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 30(12), 1956–1976. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2017.1314310>.
- 28) Lusch, R. F., & Vargo, S. L. (2014). *The service-dominant logic of marketing: Dialog, debate, and directions*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315699035>.
- 29) Lusch, R. F., Vargo, S. L., & O'brien, M. (2007). Competing through service: Insights from service-dominant logic. *Journal of Retailing*, 83(1), 5–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretai.2006.10.002>.
- 30) M. Kang, J.-Y. (2014). Repurchase loyalty for customer social co-creation e-marketplaces. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*, 18(4), 452–464. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFMM-06-2013-0083>.
- 31) Moghadamzadeh, A., Ebrahimi, P., Radfard, S., Salamzadeh, A., & Khajeheian, D. (2020). Investigating the role of customer co-creation behavior on social media platforms in rendering innovative services. *Sustainability*, 12(17), 6926. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12176926>.
- 32) Paringan, A. T., & Novani, S. (2022). The Roles of Customer Perception of Innovativeness and Engagement on Loyalty through Value Co-creation Behaviors: The Case of Food-delivery Service. *Binus Business Review*, 13(1), 81–96. <https://doi.org/10.21512/bbr.v13i1.7850>.
- 33) Prahalad, C. K., & Ramaswamy, V. (2004). Co-creation experiences: The next practice in value creation. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 18(3), 5–14. <https://doi.org/10.1002/dir.20015>.
- 34) Rathore, A. K., Ilavarasan, P. V., & Dwivedi, Y. K. (2016). Social media content and product co-creation: an emerging paradigm. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 29(1), 7–18. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEIM-06-2015-0047>.
- 35) Ren, J., Yang, J., Zhu, M., & Majeed, S. (2021). Relationship between consumer participation behaviors and consumer stickiness on mobile short video social platform under the development of ICT: based on value co-creation theory perspective. *Information Technology for Development*, 27(4), 697–717. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02681102.2021.1933882>.
- 36) Roy, S. K., Balaji, M. S., Soutar, G., & Jiang, Y. (2020). The antecedents and consequences of value co-creation behaviors in a hotel setting: A two-country study. *Cornell Hospitality Quarterly*, 61(3), 353–368. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1938965519890572>.

- 37) Seifert, C., & Kwon, W.-S. (2020). SNS eWOM sentiment: impacts on brand value co-creation and trust. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 38(1), 89–102. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MIP-11-2018-0533>.
- 38) Sharif, K., & Sidi Lemine, M. (2021). Customer service quality, emotional brand attachment and customer citizenship behaviors: Findings from an emerging higher education market. *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08841241.2021.1949659>.
- 39) Torkzadeh, S., Zolfagharian, M., & Iyer, P. (2021). Customer value co-creation behaviors and service outcomes: insights from a transformative service. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 29(8), 635–657. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0965254X.2020.1777458>.
- 40) van Tonder, E., Saunders, S. G., Lisita, I. T., & de Beer, L. T. (2018). The importance of customer citizenship behaviour in the modern retail environment: Introducing and testing a social exchange model. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 45, 92–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2018.08.011>.
- 41) Vargo, S. L., & Lusch, R. F. (2004). Evolving to a new dominant logic for marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 68(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkg.68.1.1.24036>.
- 42) Wiścicka-Fernando, M., Misiak-Kwit, S., & Fernando, K. S. D. (2019). Co-creation as an innovative way to develop an enterprise—cross-country analysis. *Sustainability*, 11(23), 6737. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11236737>.
- 43) Yen, C.-H., Teng, H.-Y., & Tzeng, J.-C. (2020). Innovativeness and customer value co-creation behaviors: Mediating role of customer engagement. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 88, 102514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102514>.
- 44) Yi, Y., & Gong, T. (2013). Customer value co-creation behavior: Scale development and validation. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(9), 1279–1284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2012.02.026>.
- 45) Yi, Y., Natarajan, R., & Gong, T. (2011). Customer participation and citizenship behavioral influences on employee performance, satisfaction, commitment, and turnover intention. *Journal of Business Research*, 64(1), 87–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2009.12.007>.
- 46) Zadeh, A. H., Zolfagharian, M., & Hofacker, C. F. (2019). Customer–customer value co-creation in social media: conceptualization and antecedents. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 27(4), 283–302. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0965254X.2017.1344289>.